

Pure and Applied Geophysics

Fractal analysis of enclaves as a new tool for estimating rheological properties of magmas during mixing: the case of Montaña Reventada (Tenerife, Canary Islands).

--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	PAAG-D-14-00259
Full Title:	Fractal analysis of enclaves as a new tool for estimating rheological properties of magmas during mixing: the case of Montaña Reventada (Tenerife, Canary Islands).
Article Type:	Report-Top.Vol. Fractals and Dynamic Systems in Geoscience
Keywords:	magma mixing; fractal analysis; Tenerife; viscosity; water content; basanite.
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Abstract:	<p>The volcanic unit of Montaña Reventada on the island of Tenerife (Canary Islands, Spain) is an example of magma mingling and mixing, in which the eruptive process was triggered by an intrusion of basanite into a phonolite magma chamber. The eruption started with the emplacement of a basanitic scoria deposit followed by the emplacement of a phonolitic lava flow characterized by the presence of mafic enclaves. These enclaves represent about 1% of the outcrop and are basanitic, phonotephritic and tephri-phonolitic in composition. The morphology of each enclave is different, varying from rounded to complex finger-like structures that usually exhibit cusped terminations. This study quantifies the textural heterogeneities related to the enclaves generated by the mixing process and thus provides a new perspective on the 1100 AD Montaña Reventada eruption. The textural study was carried out using fractal geometry and the results show that the logarithm of the viscosity ratio between the phonolitic magma and the enclaves range between 0.39 and 0.81, showing a mode at 0.49. This allows us to constrain that the water content is 2-2.5 wt% for the phonolitic magma and 1.5-2 wt% for the basanitic magma and the enclaves.</p>
Suggested Reviewers:	

1 **Fractal analysis of enclaves as a new tool for estimating**
2 **rheological properties of magmas during mixing: the case of**
3 **Montaña Reventada (Tenerife, Canary Islands).**

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11 Submitted to:
12 Report-Top.Vol. Fractals and Dynamic Systems in Geoscience
13 Pure and Applied Geophysics (PAGEOPH)

17 **Abbreviated title:** Fractal analysis as a new tool to estimate rheological properties of
18 magmas during mixing.

1 **Introduction**

2 Fractal geometry has been recently used in several studies to study mixing
3 processes. In these studies magma mixing is described as a chaotic process (Flinders
4 and Clemens, 1996; Perugini et al., 2002, 2003a, 2006; Perugini and Poli, 2000; Poli
5 and Perugini, 2002), which implies that the study of magma mixing can be
6 kinematically constrained to the study of the stretching and folding of magmas and the
7 diffusion processes that originate between them (Perugini and Poli, 2012). These studies
8 have provided a new point of view useful for calculating certain parameters related to
9 magma chamber dynamics such as the viscosity ratio between magmas and the
10 proportions of the magmas involved in the mixing process.

11 The physical mixing (mingling) of two magmas with contrasting physical
12 properties tends to result in the formation of enclaves (Perugini et al., 2007) and/or the
13 presence of flow banding, which has been described by some authors to be the result of
14 the stretching and folding of magma filaments (Perugini et al., 2003b; Perugini et al.,
15 2004). When the two magmas equilibrate thermally, chemical diffusion also occurs,
16 thereby generating compositions that are intermediate between the two initial
17 compositions (Petrelli et al., 2006; Perugini et al., 2012; Morgavi et al., 2013; Perugini
18 et al., 2013). The chemical diffusion is facilitated by the stretching and folding
19 processes because of the increase of the contact area between the two magmas.

20 During magma mixing two kinds of regions are generated (Perugini et al.,
21 2003b): coherent and the active regions. Coherent regions remain generally unaffected
22 by diffusion and therefore the composition of the original magmas is preserved. In
23 contrast with coherent regions, active regions are strongly affected by stretching and
24 folding, and chemical diffusion produces a composition that is intermediate between the

1 two magmas involved in the mixing process. This means that magma mixing should not
2 be interpreted as a linear process in which different hybrid compositions correspond to
3 different amounts of intruded magma. Typically, when a mafic magma intrudes into a
4 felsic magma chamber and mixing starts, magmas of different hybrid compositions will
5 be produced due to the generation of coherent and active regions in which the
6 proportion of the two magmas and the degrees of chemical diffusion vary (e.g. Perugini
7 et al., 2003b).

8 Magma mixing has been observed in the volcanic deposits of Tenerife (Canary
9 Islands) in pyroclastic rocks (Wolff, 1985; Martí et al., 1990; Edgar et al. 2002, 2007)
10 and lava flows (Araña, 1985; Araña et al., 1989, 1994). The products of some of these
11 eruptions provide excellent examples of magma mixing processes due to the presence of
12 enclaves and/or stretching and folding structures. One of the best known cases of
13 magma mixing on Tenerife is the 1100 AD (Carracedo et al., 2007) Montaña Reventada
14 eruption (Araña et al., 1994; Wiesmaier et al., 2011). The eruption centre is located on
15 the island's northwestern rift zone, on the southwestern flank of the Teide-Pico Viejo
16 active central volcanic complex (Ablay and Martí, 2000). The eruption, in which a batch
17 of mafic magma from deep in the rift zone probably intruded into the phonolitic
18 chamber of Teide-Pico Viejo, generated basaltic scoria followed by the emplacement of
19 a thick phonolite lava flow characterized by the presence of multiple enclaves. Previous
20 studies (Araña et al., 1994; Wiesmaier et al., 2011) focusing on the geochemistry and
21 mineralogy of the eruption products show that these enclaves are the result of mixing
22 between basanitic and phonolitic magmas. Although several studies of phonolitic
23 magma storage conditions in Tenerife have been conducted (Andújar et al., 2010, 2013;

1 Andújar and Scaillet, 2012a, 2012b), from the best of our knowledge there is no
2 information about basanitic magma.

3 In this study we aim to provide a new perspective of the 1100 AD Montaña
4 Reventada eruption by quantifying the textural heterogeneities generated by the mixing
5 process. We show that a textural study carried out using fractal geometry can be useful
6 for calculating the water content and the viscosity of the enclaves and the basanitic
7 magma, providing new and useful data about this magma.

9 **Geological setting**

10 **FIG.1**

11 Teide-Pico Viejo (TPV) started to grow about 180-190 ka ago in the interior of
12 the caldera of Las Cañadas (Ablay and Martí, 2000; Martí et al., 2008) (Fig. 1). This
13 volcanic depression originated as a result of several vertical collapses of the former
14 Tenerife central volcanic edifice (Las Cañadas edifice) caused by the explosive
15 emptying of high-level magma chambers. Occasional large-scale, lateral collapses of the
16 volcano flanks also occurred and modified the resulting caldera depression (Martí et al.,
17 1994, 1997; Martí and Gudmundsson, 2000). The construction of the present central
18 volcanic complex on Tenerife involved the formation of these twin stratovolcanoes,
19 which derive from the interaction of two different shallow magma systems that have
20 evolved simultaneously and have given rise to a complete magma series from basalt to
21 phonolite (Ablay et al., 1998; Martí et al., 2008).

22 TPV mostly consists of mafic-to-intermediate products, in which felsic materials
23 are volumetrically subordinate overall (see Martí et al., 2008). Felsic products, however,
24 predominate in the most recent eruptions that have occurred from the central vents and a

1 multitude of vents distributed on the edifice's flanks (Fig. 1). Both mafic and phonolitic
2 magmas have erupted from these vents. The Santiago del Teide and Dorsal rift axes
3 (Fig. 1), the two main tectonic lineations currently active on Tenerife, probably join
4 beneath the TPV complex (Carracedo, 1994; Ablay and Martí, 2000). Some flank vents
5 on the western side of Pico Viejo are located on eruption fissures that are sub-parallel to
6 fissures located further down the Santiago del Teide rift and define the main rift axis.
7 This is the case of the Montaña Reventada eruption (Fig. 1) studied in this paper. On the
8 eastern side of Teide some flank vents define eruption fissures that run parallel to the
9 Dorsal rift.

10 The eruptive history of the TPV comprises a main phase of eruption of mafic-to-
11 intermediate lavas that form the core of the volcanoes and also infill most of the Las
12 Cañadas depression and the adjacent La Orotava and Icod valleys. About 35 ka ago the
13 first phonolites appeared and since then have become the predominant material in the
14 TPV eruptions. Basaltic eruptions have also continued and are mostly associated with
15 the two main rift zones. Available petrological data suggest that the interaction between
16 a deep basaltic and a shallow phonolitic magmatic system beneath central Tenerife
17 controls the eruption dynamics of TPV (Martí et al., 2008). Most of the phonolitic
18 eruptions from TPV show signs of magma mixing, suggesting that eruptions are
19 triggered by the intrusion of deep basaltic magmas into shallow phonolitic reservoirs.

20 The 1100 AD Montaña Reventada eruption is a clear case of a mafic eruption in
21 the NW rift zones in which basaltic magma interacted with phonolitic magma from the
22 TPV system. The result was a Strombolian eruption that generated a welded scoria
23 deposit of basaltic composition and a phonolitic lava flow with clear evidence of
24 mixing. The basaltic scoria deposit has a maximum thickness of 2 m proximal to the

1 vent. The lava flow was mainly emplaced a few kilometres from the vent and has an
2 average thickness of 12 m. The total volume (DRE) of the deposit estimated from
3 geological mapping by Martí et al. (2008) is 0.054 km³.

5 **Methodology**

6 *Fractal dimension*

7 The enclaves contained in the phonolitic lava flow can be classified according to
8 their shapes, which vary from highly irregular to almost round (Fig. 2). A few have
9 angular profiles. Previous studies have suggested that angular enclaves correspond to
10 more mafic compositions (Araña et al., 1994; Wiesmaier et al., 2011) due to the
11 fragmentation of the contact surface between the intruding mafic magma and the cooler
12 phonolitic magma (Wiesmaier et al., 2011).

13 Photographs of 67 samples were taken normal to the surface of the enclaves in
14 order to delineate the contact between the enclaves and the host rock. The images were
15 processed using the NIH (National Institute of Health) software (ImageJ) to generate
16 binary images in which enclaves and host rock were replaced by black and white pixels,
17 respectively (Fig. 2). The contact tracing operation was repeated several times to
18 estimate the error, which was found to be about 2–3%.

19 **FIG.2**

20 Enclaves with hybrid compositions can be studied with fractal geometry to analyze the
21 morphology of their complex margins. The complexity of the morphology of the
22 enclaves was quantified by the fractal dimension (D_{box}). To compute this value the Box-
23 Counting Method was applied, which consists of placing a square mesh of various sizes

(r) over the image and then counting the number of boxes (N) that contain part of the image (Fig. 3).

FIG.3

Viscosity

Perugini and Poli (2005) proposed a method for establishing the relationship between the complexity of the morphology of the interface between two fluids and the viscosity ratio (V_R) between them. This ratio is defined as the ratio of the viscosity of the host fluid to that of the driving fluid. After several fluid-mechanical experiments they derived the following empirical relationship:

$$\log(V_R) = 0.013 * e^{3.34D_{box}} \quad (1)$$

which shows that the complexity of the interface increases with the viscosity contrast. This empirical relationship can be applied to natural cases to estimate the viscosity ratio between two magmas coming into contact during a mixing process. The relationship is valid just while the two magmas can be considered fluids, therefore before a significant amount of crystallization has occurred. In this study the viscosity ratio was calculated using the fractal dimension of the morphology of the enclaves. Since this was a bi-dimensional study D_{box} varied between 1 and 2.

To estimate the viscosity of the magmas as a function of the whole rock composition and temperature we used the model produced by Giordano et al. (2008). Whole rock analyses were taken from Wiesmaier et al. (2011) and Araña et al. (1994). Average compositions were recalculated to 100 after adding H₂O and recalculate all Fe to FeO_{tot} (Table 1). This procedure was used because the calculated viscosity ratios correspond to magmas located in the magma chamber and therefore it was necessary to

1 calculate the viscosity of magmas at plausible conditions at that depth. Previous
 2 experimental works show that phonolitic magma erupted from the Teide-Pico Viejo
 3 flank vents was stored at temperatures of $\approx 900^{\circ}\text{C}$, at pressures of $\approx 50\text{MPa}$ and with
 4 $\approx 2.5 \pm 0.5$ wt% of dissolved H_2O (Andújar et al., 2010, 2013; Andújar and Scaillet,
 5 2012a, 2012b). Based on this we have considered 2, 2.5 and 3 wt% H_2O for the
 6 phonolitic magma. Since there is no information for the basanite water content a range
 7 of 1 to 2.5 wt% H_2O was considered. An average composition of enclaves with 65-70%
 8 of basanite and 35-30% of phonolite was considered since on the Harker diagrams
 9 showed in Wiesmaier et al. (2011), which also include the analysis carried out by Araña
 10 et al. (1994), data clusters at around 65-70% of mafic magma. We consider this amount
 11 as representative of the mafic magma present in the system and the other values due to
 12 different degrees of mixing because of the actives and coherent regions. The average
 13 composition was recalculated to 100 after adding 1.5 and 2 wt% H_2O .

14 **TABLE 1**

16 **Results**

17 When the box-counting method is applied to fractal patterns the following
 18 relationship is satisfied (Mandelbrot, 1982):

19
$$N = r^{-D_{box}} \tag{2}$$

20 Equation 1 can be also written as:

21
$$\text{Log}(N) = -D_{box} * \text{Log}(r) \tag{3}$$

22 The slope of the linear interpolation of the $\text{Log}(r)$ vs. $\text{Log}(N)$ graph is equal to $-D_{box}$
 23 (Fig. 4). Fig. 4A-C shows the application of Equations 2 and 3 to the three enclaves
 24 shown in Fig. 2A-C. From A to C the D_{box} value decreases with the complexity of the

1 morphology of the interface. The D_{box} of the 67 images of the enclaves ranges between
2 1.01 and 1.23 (Fig. 5) and shows a mode at $D_{\text{box}}=1.09$. A histogram with the regression
3 coefficients of the linear interpolation is shown in Fig. 6.

4 **FIG. 4, 5 & 6**

5 The calculation of the logarithm of the viscosity ratio from D_{box} according to
6 equation 1 is shown in Figure 7. Figure 7B is a detail of Figure 7A that focuses on the
7 variation in the $\log V_R$. The $\log V_R$ range between 0.39 and 0.81 and the distribution of
8 the values are shown in Figure 8. The class with $V_R=0.49$ has the highest frequency.

9 **FIG. 7&8**

10 Knowing the viscosity of the phonolite (Table 2) and the viscosity ratio between
11 the phonolitic magma and the enclaves, the average viscosity of the enclaves can be
12 calculated as follows:

$$13 \quad V_R = \frac{\mu_{\text{phonolite}}}{\mu_{\text{enclave}}} \quad (4)$$

$$14 \quad \mu_{\text{enclave}} = \frac{\mu_{\text{phonolite}}}{V_R} \quad (5)$$

15 For the viscosity of the phonolite computed values with 2.5 ± 0.5 wt% of dissolved H_2O
16 were considered. For V_R the minimum and maximum values were considered (0.39 and
17 0.81) and also the value with the highest frequency (0.49). The obtained values are
18 summarized in Table 3.

19 **TABLE 2&3**

21 **Discussion**

22 Perugini and Poli (2005) state that different D_{box} values correspond to different
23 V_R . Accordingly, we focus here on the relationship between changes in V_R and changes
24 in magma compositions due to different degrees of mixing. More precisely, we propose

1 the existence of a mixing area in which the two magmas interacted and produced
2 magma of intermediate compositions. Some of the considered enclaves exhibit cusped
3 terminations (Fig. 2C), which have been used as evidence (Perugini et al., 2007) of the
4 detachment of the enclaves from the mafic magma and their move toward more felsic
5 magma. As Wiesmaier et al. (2011) showed some enclaves still present mingling
6 structures. Enclaves with cusped terminations, mingling structures and variable
7 compositions – and hence variable D_{box} and V_R – must have originated in this mixing
8 zone throughout the whole process.

9 In the first stage, when the basanite ($\approx 1200^\circ\text{C}$) reached the phonolite magma
10 chamber ($\approx 900^\circ\text{C}$), the more mafic enclaves, characterized by quenching and angular
11 shapes, were generated by the disruption of the layer formed as a consequence of the
12 thermic contrast between the two magmas. According to Folch and Martí (1998) and
13 Snyder (2000), during this first stage of mixing the temperature of the basanite started to
14 fall and the temperature of the phonolite to increase and hence the V_R decreases, thereby
15 facilitating the mixing process between the basanite and the phonolite. The cooling and
16 the consequent crystallization of the mafic magma generated an accumulation of gas
17 bubbles at the interface between the two magmas that gave rise in some cases to the
18 production of vesiculated blobs of mafic magma inside the felsic magma (Eichelberger,
19 1980; Thomas and Tait, 1997). This is consistent with the fact that the vesiculated
20 enclaves of Montaña Reventada have higher D_{box} (Fig.2A-B and Fig.4A-B) and are
21 therefore closer in composition to the mafic end-member. While the basanite continued
22 to ascend to the surface, mingling structures were generated in the contact area. These
23 structures were captured in the blobs of magma, which detached from this zone through
24 the felsic magma and generated enclaves. The presence of both coherent and active

1 regions yielded enclaves with different amounts of mafic and felsic magma. The
2 chemical diffusion inside the enclaves produced different hybrid compositions and
3 hence enclaves with interface morphologies characterized by different D_{box} . Some
4 enclaves display morphologies that could correspond to different D_{box} values over their
5 contours. This is consistent with the existence of coherent and active regions within the
6 same enclave. Throughout the process the mixing zone become more homogenous, due
7 to mingling and diffusion and because the V_R continued to decrease and thus to generate
8 enclaves with lower D_{box} .

9 Knowing the V_R between the phonolitic magma and the enclaves is possible to
10 estimate the range of viscosities of the enclaves. Since the viscosity is closely related to
11 the water content this allows us to estimate a plausible range of dissolved water content
12 in the enclaves. The enclaves were generated at a temperature lower than the basanite
13 and higher than the phonolite and are the result of the mixing of these two magmas with
14 different viscosities. Hence the viscosity range of the enclaves must be between the
15 basanite and the phonolite viscosity values. This constrain reduce to two the possible
16 combinations of water content of the phonolite, the basanite and the enclaves. As shown
17 in Fig.9 if the water content of the phonolite is 2 or 2.5 wt% the water content of the
18 basanite must be 1.5 or 2 wt% respectively. Since $V_R=0.49$ is a mode value it can be
19 considered related to the percentage of mafic magma present in the system and the other
20 values due to different degrees of mixing. The viscosity of the considered enclaves
21 (Table 2) overlap with the curve of $V_R=0.49$ (Table 3) for a water content of 1.5 wt% or
22 2 wt%.

23 **FIG.9**

1 Another important question concerning the Montaña Reventada eruption is
2 whether all the basanite that intruded into the phonolitic magma was erupted or not. The
3 enclaves represent just $\approx 1\%$ of the outcrop (Araña et al., 1994) and, according to
4 estimates from the stratigraphic sections in Araña et al. (1994) and Wiesmaier et al.
5 (2011), the amount of basanite erupted corresponds to up to 15% of the total erupted
6 products generated during the eruption. This suggests that residual basanite magma was
7 still stored in the magma chamber, which may have either evolved into more
8 differentiated compositions or crystallized to form a denser body. Data from subsequent
9 eruptions on Tenerife are unable to shed any further light on this question.

10 11 **Conclusions**

12 The results of the fractal study conducted on Montaña Reventada show that
13 enclaves with different D_{box} – and hence different compositions – represent different
14 degrees of mixing in the system, even though all could have been generated at the same
15 time and with the same percentage of mafic magma.

16 The fractal analysis of enclaves of Montaña Reventada offers clues to constrain
17 the dissolved water content and the viscosities of the enclaves and the basanitic magma.
18 The initial estimation, based on previous works, of the water content of the phonolite on
19 2-3 wt% can be reduce in this case to 2-2.5 wt%. Acceptable values for the basanite and
20 the enclaves range between 1.5 and 2 wt%.

21 22 **Acknowledgements**

23 H. Albert was funded by the Spanish Geographic Institute (IGN). This research was
24 partially funded by the IGN and the European Commission (FP7 630 Theme:

1 ENV.2011.1.3.3-1; Grant 282759: VUELCO). We are grateful for the help and support
2 provided by C. López, H. Lamolda and A. Felpeto. We thank the two anonymous
3 reviewers for their constructive comments that helped to improve the manuscript. We
4 also thank the Teide National Park for their permission to undertake this research. The
5 English text was corrected by Michael Lockwood.

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2 **FIGURES**
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6 **Fig. 1.** Location of the Montaña Reventada lavas (MR) and an illustration of rift zones
7 and visible vents. Black dots correspond to felsic vents and white dots to mafic and
8 intermediate vents. SRZ: Santiago rift zone; DRZ: Dorsal rift zone; LC: Las Cañadas; T:
9 Teide, PV: Pico Viejo (projection: UTM 28N). Modified from Martí et al. 2011.

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2 **Fig. 2A-C.** Examples of enclaves and their binary images. From A to C the
3 morphologies become less complex. Enclaves A and C show cusate termination.

Fig. 3. A) Original image of the enclave. B) Thresholded contact between the enclave and the host rock. C-E) Zoomed area indicated by the dashed line in Figure A. Procedure used to measure fractal dimension (D_{box}) using the box-counting method. A square mesh of various sizes (r) is laid over the contact area between the enclaves and the host rock. The number of boxes (N) containing black pixels is counted.

Table 1. Major element average from Wiesmaier et al., 2011 and Araña et al., 1994 recalculated to 100 after adding H_2O .

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(wt%)	Phonolite		Basanite				Enclaves			
	2 wt% H ₂ O	2.5 wt% H ₂ O	3 wt% H ₂ O	0.5 wt% H ₂ O	1 wt% H ₂ O	1.5 wt% H ₂ O	2 wt% H ₂ O	2.5 wt% H ₂ O	1.5 wt% H ₂ O	2 wt% H ₂ O
SiO ₂	58.05	57.76	57.46	46.79	46.55	46.32	46.08	45.85	50.24	49.98
TiO ₂	1.15	1.14	1.13	3.35	3.34	3.32	3.30	3.29	2.56	2.55
Al ₂ O ₃	18.39	18.30	18.20	17.26	17.17	17.08	16.99	16.91	17.61	17.52
FeO(tot)	4.25	4.23	4.21	10.11	10.06	10.01	9.95	9.91	7.93	7.89
MnO	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.17	0.17
MgO	1.16	1.16	1.15	4.54	4.52	4.49	4.47	4.45	3.25	3.24
CaO	2.21	2.19	2.18	9.15	9.10	9.05	9.01	8.96	6.83	6.79
Na ₂ O	7.70	7.66	7.62	4.93	4.91	4.88	4.86	4.84	6.23	6.19
K ₂ O	4.61	4.59	4.57	1.90	1.90	1.89	1.88	1.87	2.70	2.69
P ₂ O ₅	0.32	0.32	0.32	1.29	1.29	1.28	1.27	1.27	0.97	0.96
H ₂ O	2.00	2.50	3.00	0.50	1.00	1.50	2.00	2.50	1.50	2.00
Sum	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

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2 **Fig. 4A-C.** Calculation of fractal dimension (D_{box}). The slope of the linear interpolation
3 of $\text{Log}(r)$ vs. $\text{Log}(N)$ is equal to $-D_{\text{box}}$.

Fig. 5. Frequency histogram displaying the distribution of values of the fractal dimension (D_{box}) in the enclaves on Montaña Reventada.

Fig. 6. Frequency histogram displaying the distribution of values of the regression coefficients for the linear interpolation of $\text{Log}(r)$ vs. $\text{Log}(N)$. Values are always greater than 0.99, thereby demonstrating the excellent linear fitting of the data.

Fig. 7A-B. Variation of D_{box} vs. $\text{Log}(V_R)$ for the studied enclaves. A) The curve shows the exponential fit of equation 3 considering $1 < D_{\text{box}} < 2$. B) Zoom of the variation range of D_{box} vs. $\text{Log}(V_R)$ for the hybrid enclaves. Shaded area indicates the highest frequency range.

Fig. 8. Frequency histogram displaying the distribution of values of $\text{Log}(V_R)$ calculated according to equation 3. Class 0.49 corresponds to the shaded area on Fig.7B.

1 **Table 2.** Logarithm of the viscosity of the phonolite, the basanite and the enclaves with
 2 65-70% of mafic magma.

wt%H ₂ O	Phonolite			Basanite				Enclaves			
	2	2.5	3	0.5	1	1.5	2	2.5	1.5	2	
T (°C)	log μ (Pa·s)										
900	4.11	3.83	3.57	4.28	3.75	3.43	3.19	3.00	3.77	3.49	
1000	3.31	3.06	2.84	3.13	2.72	2.47	2.28	2.13	2.84	2.62	
1100	2.64	2.42	2.23	2.24	1.92	1.71	1.56	1.43	2.11	1.92	
1200	2.07	1.88	1.71	1.54	1.28	1.10	0.97	0.87	1.50	1.34	

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1 **Table 3.** Logarithm of the viscosity of the enclaves calculated accordingly with the V_R
 2 values and the viscosity of the phonolite.

Phonolite	2 wt% H ₂ O			2.5 wt% H ₂ O		
	V_R	0.39	0.49	0.81	0.39	0.49
T(°C)	Enclaves log μ (Pa·s)					
900	3.72	3.62	3.30	3.44	3.34	3.02
1000	2.92	2.82	2.50	2.67	2.57	2.25
1100	2.25	2.15	1.83	2.03	1.93	1.61
1200	1.68	1.58	1.26	1.49	1.39	1.07

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Fig. 9. Variation of logarithm of viscosity with temperature.

Figure1
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Figure2
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Figure4
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Figure9A
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Figure9B
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Table 2. Logarithm of the viscosity of the phonolite, the basanite and the enclaves with 65-70% of mafic magma.

wt%H ₂ O	Phonolite			Basanite				Enclaves		
	2	2.5	3	0.5	1	1.5	2	2.5	1.5	2
T (°C)	log μ (Pa·s)									
900	4.11	3.83	3.57	4.28	3.75	3.43	3.19	3.00	3.77	3.49
1000	3.31	3.06	2.84	3.13	2.72	2.47	2.28	2.13	2.84	2.62
1100	2.64	2.42	2.23	2.24	1.92	1.71	1.56	1.43	2.11	1.92
1200	2.07	1.88	1.71	1.54	1.28	1.10	0.97	0.87	1.50	1.34

Table 3. Logarithm of the viscosity of the enclaves calculated accordingly with the V_R values and the viscosity of the phonolite.

Phonolite	2 wt% H ₂ O			2.5 wt% H ₂ O		
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T(°C)	Enclaves log μ (Pa·s)					
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1000	2.92	2.82	2.50	2.67	2.57	2.25
1100	2.25	2.15	1.83	2.03	1.93	1.61
1200	1.68	1.58	1.26	1.49	1.39	1.07